

SELF-EFFICACY: CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS AND CRUCIAL FINDINGS

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The concept of self-efficacy refers to how well one can perform a course of action that is required in a specific situation. Thus, it is an expectation that will determine whether an individual will be able to exhibit coping behaviour and how long effort will be sustained even in the face of obstacles.

Key Features:

- * Not a general trait but a differentiated set of self-beliefs that function differently in specific domains
- * Not a fixed capacity but is dependent on the particular area of endeavour
- * Self-efficacy is also dependent on the beliefs on what we can do, depending on specific circumstances
- * Different from self-esteem, which is a general trait. Yet self-efficacy has a profound effect on perception of the self
- * Has major effects on attributions of success and failure
- * Also has strong effects on persistence and sustaining motivation

CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS

Albert Bandura (1997) suggests that self-efficacy has a major role in how we approach tasks. He relates the concept to his earlier views on social cognitive theory and the significance of observational and other forms of learning. In his view there are four major sources of self-efficacy.

The first and major source of self-efficacy is through mastery experience. Nothing is more powerful than having a direct experience of mastery to increase self-efficacy. Having a success, for example in mastering a task, builds self-belief in that task whereas a failure will have the opposite effect on efficacy belief.

The second source of self-efficacy comes from our observation of people around us, especially people we consider as role models. Seeing people succeed by their effort raises our beliefs that we too have the capacity to master the activities needed for success in that area.

Influential people in our lives such as parents and teachers can strengthen our beliefs that we have what it takes to succeed. Being persuaded that we possess the ability to master certain activities means that we are more likely to put in the effort and sustain it when problems arise.

A person's physical and psychological state will influence how they judge self-efficacy. Depression, for example, can dampen our confidence. Stress reactions or tension are interpreted as signs of vulnerability to poor performance whereas positive emotions can boost our confidence in our skills.

SELF-EFFICACY VS. GENERAL MEASURES

Traditional measure of attributes served several purposes. There was a tendency to omit information about the specifics of the situation. Measures are usually couched in a general form. Often self-reports on achievement omit specific subject areas, the specific conditions and circumstances that can affect likelihood of success including motivational factors.

For example, the Locus of Control Scale is widely used to gauge the extent to which people see events are within or outside their control. The problem is that there is a variety of factors which impinge on this perception and these need to be taken into account in devising scales, and this is the essence of what self-efficacy measures try to do. Efficacy beliefs vary on several dimensions and these have important implications. A major factor to be taken into account concerns demands that represent various degrees of challenge to achieve a successful performance. If there are no obstacles, the activity is easy and most people have a high perceived self-efficacy for that task, while challenges and obstacles result in relatively lower scores. For these reasons, in devising tests, there is a need to analyse what it takes to succeed in a given domain.

Efficacy beliefs also vary in terms of generality. We can be efficacious across a range of activities or only in specific domains. Efficacy beliefs also vary in strength. In the case of weak efficacy beliefs, these can be wiped out easily by a disconfirming experience while with firm beliefs these will persist even in the face of obstacles.

SELF-EFFICACY IN KEY AREAS

Here we consider the importance of self-efficacy in four areas that have received special interest in recent research. The first of these is concerned with the effect of self-efficacy on the performance of students in higher education while the second focuses on teacher self-efficacy and its impact on classroom interaction and students' achievement as well as teachers' own well-being. We will also look at research on the importance of self-efficacy for brain health of older adults as well as its importance in addressing educational disadvantage.

An especially valuable review of the impact of academic self-efficacy on learning performance (ASE) has been carried out by Honicke & Broadbent (2016) based on 59 studies examining this issue between 2003 and 2015. There were two major questions: (i) what is the strength of the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic performance? and (ii) what mediating and moderating factors have been investigated to explain the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic performance of university students and what do they report?

Overall meta-analytic findings suggest that a moderate positive relationship exists between academic self-efficacy and academic performance, but there is significant heterogeneity across studies, which is accounted for partly by inter-study differences in operationalization of self-efficacy and academic performance. Additionally, it appears that the mechanism in which ASE relates to and influences academic performance is mediated through such variables as effort regulation and academic procrastination.

These results suggest that a student's ability to regulate the amount of effort dedicated to learning tasks, in the face of boredom or other distractions, partially facilitates and explains the relationship between self-efficacy and performance. It appears the higher a student's level of academic self-efficacy, the more likely effort will be expended on a learning task, which is likely to result in greater levels of academic performance. This is a logical conclusion and is supported by previous research findings.

A meta-analysis by Zee & Koomen (2016) provides a synthesis of 165 studies that examined the importance of teacher self-efficacy (TSE) for a range of outcomes with a particular focus on quality of classroom interactions, students' academic outcomes and the well-being of teachers and students. Results showed positive relationships between TSE and students' academic achievement as well as their quality of learning. TSE was also found to have an influence on the interaction of teachers and students as well as various factors that contribute to teachers' psychological well-being including job satisfaction and commitment to teaching.

Conversely, there were negative effects on various measures of teacher burnout. Furthermore, a number of students were identified that demonstrated a range of indirect effects of TSE. For example, TSE impacted on academic adjustment and psychological well-being through classroom organisation. These findings underline the range of complexity of the impact of TSE on children and teachers.

Of the recent areas that have been examined, the findings regarding the relationship between self-efficacy and brain health are of particular note. A major concern for our aging population is around the factors that influence cognitive decline. Several factors have been identified that prevent such deterioration including involvement in social and intellectually challenging activities. There is now evidence that one's personal perceived ability to perform a specific task impacts on performance. A study by Horst & Nagamatsu (2018) sought to explore a relationship between measures of Memory self-efficacy and standardised cognitive tests. They explored this relationship while taking into account other relevant factors including age and level of physical activity. The results of this study suggest that Memory self-efficacy is indeed related to actual performance on tasks requiring remembering. The relationship was strong and accounted for 65% of the variance even after considering other factors.

An important question is around the possible role of self-efficacy in addressing educational disadvantage. This is of special importance given the potential benefits of new approaches to enhancing the performance of children from disadvantaged backgrounds. One line of research by Zahodne et al., (2015) is especially promising. In a national study including adults from 30 to 85 years, it emerged that people with low education, but high self-efficacy performed as well as people with high education. Their study provides evidence that self-efficacy beliefs can buffer against the effects of low levels of education and the associated negative impact on school performance. Thus, there is real promise on how the damaging effect of educational disadvantage can be addressed.

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